

1 Evolution of fabric anisotropy of granular soils:
2 x-ray tomography measurements and theoretical modelling

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8 **Abstract**

9 Fabric anisotropy is a key component to understand the behaviour of granular soils. In general,
10 experimental data on fabric anisotropy for real granular soils are very limited, especially in the critical
11 state. In this paper, x-ray tomography measurements are used to provide experimental data on contact
12 fabric anisotropy inside shear bands for two granular soils. The data are then used to assess the validity of
13 Anisotropic Critical State Theory (ACST) and the accuracy of a fabric evolution law that was previously
14 developed from the results of DEM simulations on idealised materials.

15 Overall, the experimental results support ACST according to which unique (*i.e.*, independent of initial
16 conditions) values for fabric anisotropy and coordination number are observed at large strains. With
17 increasing roundness of the material, the rate at which the critical state is approached increases. The
18 evolution of fabric anisotropy measured from the experiments is fairly well reproduced by the proposed
19 evolution law.

20 *Keywords:* Granular soils, fabric anisotropy, shear band, x-ray tomography, Anisotropic Critical State
21 Theory

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23 In this issue commemorating Prof. G. Pande, we would like to dedicate this work to his memory. In
 24 our minds, there are interesting links to be made between his work on soil anisotropy [1] and the current
 25 study on Anisotropic Critical State Theory.

26 1. Introduction

27 Granular soils are composed of solid particles and interparticle voids that are filled with one or more
 28 fluids. The arrangement of particles and voids involves the distribution of their sizes and orientations.
 29 Furthermore, it is important (for the force transmission) which particles are in contact. The microstruc-
 30 ture includes the arrangement of particles, voids and interparticle contacts. This microstructure has a
 31 significant influence on the behaviour of granular soils, in particular on the shear strength and dilatancy,
 32 as has been shown by experiments [2–4], micromechanical studies [5–15] and Discrete Element Method
 33 (as proposed in [16]; *DEM* for short) simulations [17–24].

34 To quantify the microstructure, a second-order *fabric tensor* [9, 11, 13, 19, 20, 25–32] is usually
 35 employed, whose deviatoric part has been generally used to describe *fabric anisotropy* of granular soils.
 36 Various fabric tensors have been defined in the literature [11, 25, 33], that differ in the involved micro-
 37 scale quantities. The description of the microstructure is based either on particle orientations [25], or
 38 on orientation vectors \mathbf{u}^c associated with the interparticle contacts c [19, 34], or (less frequently) on the
 39 orientation of the voids [11, 35, 36].

40 Examples of such micro-scale vectors \mathbf{u}^c are: (i) the vector normal to the contact plane (here referred
 41 to as contact normal) [28], (ii) the branch vector [37–39] and (iii) the void vector [11, 35, 36]. In this study,
 42 a fabric tensor based on interparticle contacts is considered, which is attractive since force transmission
 43 occurs at contacts.

44 The definition of a symmetric second-order fabric tensor \mathbf{G} is based on the micro-scale vectors \mathbf{u}^c

$$45 \quad \mathbf{G} = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{c=1}^{N_c} \mathbf{u}^c \otimes \mathbf{u}^c \quad \mathbf{F} = \frac{5}{2(1+e)} (3\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{I}) , \quad (1)$$

46 where N_c is the total number of contacts and e is the void ratio of the volume under consideration. Hence
 47 the fabric tensor \mathbf{G} is an average of (the dyadic product of) the vectors \mathbf{u}^c that are associated with
 48 interparticle contacts. The dimensionless *fabric anisotropy tensor* \mathbf{F} in Eq. (1) (right), that is studied in
 49 the following and that has been widely used in the literature [40, 41], is proportional to the *deviatoric* part
 50 of the fabric tensor \mathbf{G} . Note that \mathbf{F} is scaled with the specific volume, as suggested in [42]. The (scalar)
 51 norm F , termed as *fabric anisotropy*, and the direction tensor \mathbf{n}_F of the fabric tensor \mathbf{F} are defined by

$$52 \quad F = \sqrt{\mathbf{F} : \mathbf{F}} \quad \mathbf{F} = F \mathbf{n}_F . \quad (2)$$

53 The direction tensor \mathbf{n}_F satisfies $\mathbf{n}_F : \mathbf{n}_F = 1$ and $\text{tr}(\mathbf{n}_F) = 0$.

54 The relationship between continuum, macro-scale shear strength, and micro-scale interparticle forces
55 is quantitatively expressed by the stress-force-fabric relationship [7, 43–48] that also involves *fabric*
56 anisotropy. Analogously, the strain-displacement-fabric relationship quantitatively expresses the rela-
57 tionship between continuum, macro-scale dilatancy rate, and micro-scale, interparticle deformation [15].

58 In order to understand the evolution of fabric in granular soils under loading, three aspects are
59 important: (1) inherent, initial anisotropy, (2) fabric evolution, and (3) fabric at the critical state [41, 49].

60 Since the fabric is important to the behaviour of granular soils, it may be expedient to include a fabric
61 tensor into continuum-mechanical models [1, 41, 50–54]. Then a *fabric evolution law* is required. Fabric
62 evolution laws can be categorised with respect to the variables considered to be relevant for the fabric
63 rate: (i) stress ratio rate, current fabric tensor, and void ratio [55, 56]; (ii) (plastic) strain rate, current
64 fabric tensor and void ratio [49, 57, 58]; (iii) (plastic) strain rate as well as stress ratio rate, current stress
65 and fabric tensors and void ratio [49, 50, 59, 60]; and (iv) a plastic loading index, and the current fabric
66 tensor [41, 50–53, 61, 62].

67 According to the classical Critical State Theory (*CST* for short) [63, 64], for large deformations
68 a granular material continues deforming under shear at constant stress and void ratio. This state is
69 generally considered to be unique, *i.e.*, independent of the initial state of the material. The uniqueness of
70 the fabric anisotropy in this critical state [63, 64] has long been controversial. Recently, results of DEM
71 simulations have shown that fabric anisotropy approaches asymptotic unique values [14, 18, 24, 40, 65–
72 67]. Li and Dafalias [61] extended CST in their Anisotropic Critical State Theory (*ACST* for short)
73 framework, according to which the stress ratio $\eta = q/p$, where q is the deviatoric stress and p is the mean
74 stress, the void ratio e and the fabric anisotropy F (defined in Eq. (2)) of granular soils must satisfy the
75 following conditions for large deformations:

$$76 \quad \eta = \eta_c = M \quad e = e_c(p) \quad F = F_c. \quad (3)$$

77 The last additional condition forms the extension of ACST over CST. ACST was initially motivated by
78 observations of results of DEM simulations, and has been theoretically related to Gibbs stability condition
79 [61].

80 Coordination number, *i.e.*, the average number of contacts per particle, is readily quantified from
81 results of DEM simulations. Such simulations indicate that at large deformations a critical coordination
82 number is attained (*i.e.*, a steady value that is independent of the initial conditions, such as void ratio)
83 [66, 68, 69]. To the best of our knowledge, however, experimental results for granular soils on the evolution
84 of coordination number have not been reported in the literature.

85 DEM simulations have been employed to study the effect of fabric on the behaviour of granular
86 soils. Generally, the particles in such simulations correspond to spheres or ‘clumps’ consisting of several
87 spherical particles (although more sophisticated shape descriptions exist such as [70–72]). Furthermore,
88 simplified (Coulomb friction type) contact laws are adopted [18, 40, 67]. Although DEM simulations
89 provide very detailed information on particle positions and displacements as well as interparticle forces,
90 these *idealisations* are rather different from granular soils that have various shapes, surface roughnesses
91 and interparticle contact laws.

92 With such DEM simulations, samples with various inherent anisotropy can be generated by gravity de-
93 position or by the radius expansion method, and the evolution of fabric can be quantitatively determined,
94 see for instance [14, 40, 65–67, 73]. The DEM simulation results show that inherent fabric anisotropy,
95 initial void ratio and loading direction have a significant influence on the behaviour of granular soils
96 [18, 24, 40, 49, 67].

97 Experimental studies on fabric of granular systems initially focused on the effect of inherent anisotropy
98 on the macroscopic stress-strain response, where the initial orientation of the particles was controlled, and
99 the macroscopic response was measured. Results of hollow cylinder torsion tests [2, 3, 74], plane strain
100 tests [75–77] and triaxial compression and extension tests [75, 77] demonstrated that the initial fabric
101 strongly affects the overall, macroscopic stress-strain behaviour.

102 Although these results have shown the importance of fabric to the behaviour of granular systems,
103 quantitative measurements of fabric evolution within samples were not feasible. Through the use of two-
104 dimensional assemblies, in combination with experimental techniques such as photoelasticity [78, 79] and
105 stereophotogrammetry [80], the evolution of fabric within the sample under several loading paths was
106 measured.

107 For *three-dimensional* systems, x-ray tomography imaging (see [81] and the references cited therein)
108 is an ideal tool to measure the evolution of material fabric (particle orientation fabric, contact fabric,
109 branch vector fabric), since it allows for the generation of a complete three-dimensional representation of
110 the specimen at any point during the test. Nonetheless, retrieving *contact fabric* with x-ray tomography
111 presents several technical challenges, especially with respect to the detection of interparticle contacts
112 [82, 83].

113 A recent x-ray tomography study [84] considered the effect of the initial void ratio of the sample and of
114 the confining pressure. The evolution of contact-normal fabric (where \mathbf{u}^c in Eq. (1) equals the vector \mathbf{n}^c
115 normal to the contact plane) anisotropy of four different granular materials was measured, where the fabric
116 of the *whole sample* was quantified. It was found that initial void ratio, confining pressure and particle
117 morphology greatly affect the evolution of fabric anisotropy. At large deformations, the experimental

118 results show that fabric anisotropy approaches a constant value, possibly a critical state value. However,
119 samples generally become heterogeneous due to the emergence of shear bands (*i.e.*, regions where shear
120 strains localise), and inside them higher strains are achieved, compared to the outside [85]. This implies
121 that fabric inside shear bands may approach critical state conditions, even for smaller strains of the whole
122 sample. To assess the validity of the ACST framework, it is therefore important to experimentally study
123 fabric evolution *inside shear bands*.

124 The evolution of contact fabric inside shear bands was first studied in [86] for samples of angular
125 Hostun sand and round Caicos ooids. Using an observation window inside the shear band, as well as an
126 observation window outside of the shear band, contact fabric was measured at several axial deformation
127 levels. Before the beginning of the localisation process, contact fabric behaves similarly in both windows,
128 while it significantly differs once the shear band emerges. The general results for both samples are similar,
129 presenting a difference in anisotropy values and rate of change, indicating the influence of particle shape
130 and interparticle friction.

131 To describe the evolution of fabric, a rate-form evolution law for the fabric tensor has recently been
132 proposed by Zhao and Kruyt [49], based on DEM simulation results from the literature. This evolution law
133 involves critical-state fabric anisotropy, current fabric, stress ratio, loading direction and rate of deviatoric
134 plastic strain. The influence of void ratio is accounted for through the state parameter [87]. This fabric
135 evolution law is consistent with ACST and has been validated with results of DEM simulations on *idealised*
136 *materials*, showing both hardening and softening behaviour and properly describing the influence of the
137 initial void ratio. Therefore, it is important to assess its accuracy in predicting fabric evolution of *real*
138 granular materials.

139 Considering the limitations in previous studies described above, the objectives of this study are to
140 (i): present x-ray tomography measurements (involving an additional value for the confining stress in
141 comparison to [86]) of the evolution of fabric anisotropy inside shear bands of Hostun sand and Caicos
142 ooids and compare it with that outside shear bands; (ii) experimentally investigate the validity of ACST
143 and (iii) assess the accuracy of the fabric evolution law by [49] in predicting the measured fabric evolution
144 of granular soils.

145 The outline of this paper is as follows. In Section 2, the x-ray tomography experiments performed for
146 measuring the evolution of fabric anisotropy of granular soils under triaxial compression are presented.
147 In Section 3, experimental results are shown. In Section 4, the capability of the evolution law in [49]
148 is investigated by modelling the measured evolution of fabric anisotropy inside shear bands. Section 5
149 discusses the contributions of this study and the open issues on this topic.

150 2. X-ray tomography measurements of contact fabric anisotropy

151 In this Section, the properties of the tested granular soils are described, and the methodologies are
152 introduced that are employed for identifying grains, tracking them to measure local strain as well as
153 quantifying the contact-normal based fabric tensor and its evolution.

154 2.1. Tested materials, experimental setup and image analysis

155 The experiments analysed in this study comprise triaxial compression tests on two different materials:
156 Hostun sand and Caicos ooids. Caicos ooids are round calcitic, oolitic grains from Turks and Caicos
157 islands with a mean diameter $D_{50} = 420 \mu\text{m}$, whereas Hostun sand consists of angular grains from the
158 Rhône-Alpes region in France with $D_{50} = 338 \mu\text{m}$. All experiments are conducted on dry specimens that
159 are prepared by pluviation into a thin latex membrane. They are carried out inside the x-ray scanner
160 at Laboratoire 3SR in Grenoble (France), allowing for the acquisition of numerous x-ray scans of the
161 specimens during shearing. Axial compression is applied from below with a loading ram with a hemi-
162 spherical cap, allowing the bottom platen of the specimen to rotate. Axial force and displacement are
163 the only externally-measured quantities, while volume changes are obtained directly by analysing the
164 acquired images.

165 Sample sizes are set by optimising a trade-off between pixel-size (small sample) and field of view com-
166 bined with the representativeness of the mechanical response (large sample) [88]. The samples therefore
167 have a relatively small size of 11 mm in diameter, 22 mm in height, and consist of more than 40,000 grains
168 for Hostun sand samples, and more than 70,000 grains for Caicos ooids samples. The tomographies are
169 acquired at a pixel size of $15 \mu\text{m}$, which for example resolves the Hostun sand grains with 22.5 pixels across
170 the average grain diameter. Table 1 presents a summary of the initial state for each sample. Details on the
171 experiments HNMWTC02 and HNMWTC05 are given in [89] and on HNEA01, COEA01 and COEA04
172 in [90]. Additionally, the use of x-ray tomography allows for a complete 3D description of the shape of
173 the particles using several indices, such as sphericity, roundness, and aspect ratio. Results for the two
174 materials used here are given in [91].

175 During each test, the loading of the specimen is halted at chosen axial strain levels to perform x-ray
176 scans. The 3D grey-scale volumes, resulting from each x-ray scan, are used to identify and track each
177 grain throughout the test. Firstly, the two phases within the sample, *i.e.*, solid and void, are distinguished
178 based on their grey level and a binary image is created. Subsequently, the binary image is segmented
179 using a watershed algorithm [92] and each identified grain is labelled uniquely. Particle quantities, such
180 as the centre of mass, volume, and orientation, can directly be computed from this labelled image.

181 The determination of the interparticle contacts is more complex and can be prone to errors. It follows
182 the proposed technique from [82] (with a higher local threshold for Caicos to exclude overcounted contacts,

Table 1: Initial parameters of experimental samples, from [88–90]. The relative density of the Caicos ooids specimens could not be measured, due to the very limited amount of available material. Quantities in the last two columns are measured inside the region of the sample that will eventually become a shear band.

Test ID	Void Ratio (relative density)	Confining Pressure [kPa]	Fabric Anisotropy (inside shear band)	Coordination Number (inside shear band)
HNEA01	0.658 (83%)	100	0.299	6.25
HNMWTC02	0.661 (83%)	100	0.097	7.18
HNMWTC05	0.655 (85%)	400	0.166	7.14
COEA01	0.544 (–)	100	0.056	5.63
COEA04	0.610 (–)	100	0.135	5.23

183 since the problem is worse for flatter contacts). The contact normal orientations are then determined by
184 performing an additional segmentation with the random walker [93] on each pair of contacting grains.
185 The orientations are measured by performing a principal component analysis on the point cloud defining
186 the contact zone. All image analyses are performed using the open-source software *spam* [94].

187 2.2. Quantifying fabric and fabric evolution

188 Once the contacts c have been detected and the associated contact orientation \mathbf{n}^c have been obtained,
189 the contact-normal based fabric tensor and its deviatoric part can be quantified by Eq. (1).

190 The required fabric input for the evolution law of [49] is the fabric tensor inside the emerging shear
191 band. Therefore, we concentrate on the determination of contact fabric in the region of strain localisation.
192 An analysis of the contact fabric of the experiments HNEA01 and COEA01 was already presented in [86].
193 The fabric was extracted in two observation windows that are fixed in space: one inside the emerging
194 shear band and one outside. Each window contains between 2,800 and 4,800 grains. Only results from
195 these windows are presented in this study. Fig. 1 shows these two windows in a 3D rendering of Hostun
196 sand specimen HNEA01 at large axial strain.

Figure 1: Visualisation of the location of the observation windows in Hostun sand specimen (HNEA01) at large axial strain (after [89]).

197 2.3. Measurement of grain kinematics and local strain

198 Using the labelled image as the definition of the grains in a given tomography volume, the displacement
 199 and rotation of each grain between images is measured with Discrete Digital Image/Volume Correlation,
 200 as first used in [95] and implemented in the SPAM-DDIC script (see for example [96]). Concisely, this means
 201 that using the labelled image of each grain as a mask, the grey level from the reference image is extracted
 202 and an iterative procedure is used to seek the best transformation of the deformed image that minimises
 203 a sum-of-squares residual function. The result of this discrete correlation is a transformation function for
 204 each label (*i.e.*, grain) from the reference image, where labels are defined, to a given deformed image.

205 In this study, each image is labelled independently of the others and discrete correlation is performed
 206 with the next image, meaning that the granular displacement fields are incremental. Incremental local
 207 strains are obtained with Bagi's method [97], which involves a Delaunay triangulation based on the grain
 208 centres. These local strains are explicitly required as (one of the) input to the model that will be used in
 209 Section 4, to predict the evolution of fabric anisotropy.

210 3. Experimental results

211 In this Section the experimental results, including the evolution of stress and void ratio (Section 3.1),
 212 the final morphology of the shear band (Section 3.2), fabric anisotropy (Section 3.3), and coordination
 213 number (Section 3.4) are examined in the light of the ACST. The evolution of void ratio and fabric
 214 anisotropy are presented in observation windows inside as well as outside the emerging shear bands.

215 3.1. Stress ratio and void ratio

216 The macroscopic response of the experiments on Hostun sand is plotted in Fig. 2(a), where the
 217 stress relaxation parts correspond to the points where the scans have been performed. Tests HNEA01

218 and HNMWTC02 are carried out at a cell pressure of 100 kPa, whereas test HNMWTC05 is conducted
 219 at 400 kPa. The experiments were performed by different experimenters and with a different purpose
 220 in mind. HNEA01 was purposefully sheared up to relatively large strain, to study strain localisation,
 221 whereas the latter two experiments included several load reversals as these tests are part of a study that
 222 focused on fabric evolution during cyclic loading [89]; these cycles will not be considered in this study,
 223 but are shown for completeness. Unfortunately, the continuous recording of force and displacement failed
 224 for test HNMWTC05, and only the macroscopic states at which the tomographies were acquired could be
 225 reconstructed. These are marked by the red points in the plot, which are simply connected to each other
 226 with dashed lines.

227 The stress ratio response of test HNEA01 differs substantially from that of the other two tests.
 228 HNEA01 shows a higher initial stiffness as well as an earlier peak of the stress ratio, although it is initially
 229 slightly denser than HNMWTC02 and is otherwise carried out with the same macroscopic boundary
 230 conditions. It has to be noted that the specimens also differ in the initial fabric, which may be responsible
 231 for the different macroscopic response. This will be elaborated in the corresponding section.

Figure 2: Test results for Hostun sand: (a) evolution of stress ratio $\eta = q/p$ with global axial strain; (b) evolution of void ratio with global axial strain inside (dashed line) and outside (continuous line) the emerging shear band; (c) relation between void ratio and mean stress inside (dashed line) and outside (continuous line) the emerging shear band, and the critical state line from Li [98].

232 Since only the void ratio inside the emerging shear band is considered for the modelling in Section
 233 4, the void ratios are computed in the same observation windows as the contact fabric. The evolution
 234 of void ratio with the macroscopic axial strain is plotted in Fig. 2(b) for the Hostun sand specimens.
 235 The results for the two observation windows show that the specimens start to behave heterogeneously at
 236 approximately 3% of macroscopic axial strain, which can be interpreted as the onset of strain localisation.
 237 From this value of axial strain, the void ratios in the windows diverge, *i.e.*, the void ratio inside the shear
 238 band starts to increase whereas it either decreases or stays constant outside the emerging shear band.

239 The void ratios in specimen HNEA01 are slightly higher than in the other two specimens, but follow a
 240 similar evolution. HNEA01 is also the only test that reaches a steady void ratio at the end of shearing.

241 Fig. 2(c) shows the evolution of the void ratios inside and outside the shear bands as a function of
 242 mean stress. As a reference, the critical state line of Hostun sand reported by [98], which was obtained
 243 from conventional triaxial compression tests, is also plotted. This critical state line lies in between the
 244 final void ratios inside and outside of the shear band, which is understandable, since it represents a
 245 sample-wide average over regions with different levels of shear strain.

Figure 3: Test results for Caicos ooids: (a) evolution of stress ratio with global axial strain; (b) evolution of void ratio with global axial strain inside (dashed line) and outside (continuous line) the emerging shear band; (c) relation between void ratio and mean stress inside (dashed line) and outside (continuous line) the emerging shear band.

246 The macroscopic response obtained from two tests on Caicos ooids is shown in Fig. 3(a), and once
 247 again, the stress relaxation parts correspond to the points where the scans have been performed. The
 248 evolution of stress ratio in both samples is qualitatively similar: both curves exhibit a pronounced peak
 249 stress ratio before softening to a steady value. The only difference is the higher stress peak in test
 250 COEA01, which is likely due to the lower initial relative density (see Table 1). Qualitatively, void ratios
 251 inside and outside the emerging shear band show a similar evolution as for Hostun sand. The onset of
 252 strain localisation occurs earlier than for Hostun sand, between 1 and 2% global axial strain. Afterwards,
 253 the specimens dilate strongly inside the shear band, while void ratio stays constant, or slightly reduces
 254 outside the shear band. In both tests, a constant void ratio is reached at the end, which can be interpreted
 255 as the critical state – in fact, stress ratio is also constant at the end of the two tests. Note that this was
 256 also the case for test HNEA01, but not for the other two tests on Hostun sand, which were stopped at a
 257 lower axial strain.

258 3.2. Shear band morphology

259 The orientation and thickness of shear bands are known to depend on mean stress and particle shape.
 260 In order to explore the different shear band morphologies obtained in round Caicos ooids and angular
 261 Hostun sand, Fig. 4 shows the (vertical slices through the 3D) fields of particle rotations measured in the
 262 last increment of each test. Given that the rotation of the particles is a 3D vector, only the magnitude of
 263 the rotation is shown. Note that the axial strain level and the length of the selected axial strain increment
 264 vary from one test to another. For Hostun sand samples (HNEA01, HNMWTC02, and HNMWTC05),
 265 the axial strain at the beginning of the increment is 13.3%, 10.3%, and 10.2%, respectively, whereas the
 266 length of the axial strain increment is 1.5%, 2.6%, and 2.6%, respectively. For the Caicos ooids samples
 267 (COEA01 and COEA04), the axial strain level at the beginning of the increment is 10.9% and 8.9%, while
 268 the length of the axial strain increment is 0.9% and 1.3%, respectively.

Figure 4: Magnitude of incremental 3D grain rotation vectors for the last increment in each test.

269 Clear differences can be observed from one test to another. Both samples of Caicos ooids present
 270 a well defined and established shear band, with a thickness of 8 – 10 times D_{50} ; grain rotations inside
 271 the shear band are relatively large, with a mean rotation of 15° and several particles rotating more than
 272 25° . As for Hostun sand, in sample HNMWTC02 the shear band is 12 – 15 times D_{50} thick, with a
 273 mean rotation of 9° . In sample HNMWTC05, which was sheared at a confinement 4 times larger than
 274 HNMWTC02, grain rotations are less localised in space, *i.e.*, the shear band is much thicker (15 – 20
 275 times D_{50}) and the mean grain rotation is lower (5°). Interestingly, HNEA01 shows a narrow shear band
 276 with a width of 8 – 11 times D_{50} , similar to Caicos ooids, although with a lower mean rotation (6°). This
 277 narrower shear band in HNEA01, as compared to the other two tests on Hostun sand, is possibly related
 278 to the significantly higher initial value of fabric anisotropy (see Table 1), as will be discussed in the next
 279 section.

280 The inverse proportionality between the magnitude of the grain rotation and the width of the shear
281 band can be explained due to the angularity of the particles and the interlocking potential between them
282 [88]. Angular grains (as Hostun sand) develop a highly interlocked structure, restricting the particles to
283 low levels of rotation, while inducing secondary rotations of the surrounding grains — thus increasing the
284 width of the shear band. Rounded grains (as Caicos ooids) on the other hand, can rotate more freely
285 without significantly affecting adjacent particles — thus developing narrow shear bands and presenting
286 higher particle rotation. Additionally, the relation between interlocking potential and grain rotation can
287 be extended to understand the effect of the confining pressure. Sample HNMWTC05 is sheared at a
288 higher confining pressure than HNMWTC02 and HNEA01, thus making grain rotation more difficult,
289 which results in a wider shear band with lower magnitude of grain rotations, as shown in Fig. 4.

290 *3.3. Evolution of fabric anisotropy*

291 Fig. 5 shows the evolution of fabric anisotropy as defined in Eq. (2). The error in determining contact
292 orientations that was quantified in [? ?] Similarly to the void ratio, fabric anisotropy is measured in
293 the observation windows inside and outside of the emerging shear band. In the experiments on Hostun
294 sand, fabric anisotropy evolves similarly in both windows until the onset of strain localisation. Once a
295 shear band forms, fabric anisotropy inside the shear band substantially increases, whereas it rapidly levels
296 off outside the band. The only notable exception to the above is specimen HNMWTC05, where fabric
297 anisotropy keeps increasing also outside of the shear band. The reason for this can be understood by
298 looking at the much wider region of strain localization in this specimen (see Fig. 4); in these conditions, it
299 is to be expected that fabric anisotropy evolves in the whole sample throughout the test. The increasing
300 anisotropy is a result of the change in contact orientations. With ongoing shear, the orientations align
301 with the major principal stress direction. This is caused partly by contacts being lost perpendicular to
302 and gained in the direction of the loading. Most of the contacts, however, persist through the loading
303 increments and change their orientation. The contact kinematics will be studied in detail elsewhere as
304 they are not crucial for this work.

305 It is worth noting that in all tests the initial value of fabric anisotropy is the same in the two observation
306 windows, which indicates the relative homogeneity of fabric in the specimen before shearing. Sample
307 HNMWTC02 is the only exception, with a difference of about 0.1 between the initial values of anisotropy
308 in the two windows. Interestingly, although fabric anisotropy is initially lower in the region that will
309 eventually be inside the shear band, it increases during shearing, rapidly surpasses the value outside the
310 shear band, and ends up reaching almost the same value as in test HNMWTC05. The fabric of a complete
311 sample, however, is not necessarily as homogeneous as in these examples. Note that we only present the
312 response for two observation windows within the specimens. For the initial state of specimen HNMWTC02

313 we identified variations of void ratio, coordination number and fabric anisotropy of roughly ± 0.025 , 0.25
 314 and 0.15, respectively, in absolute values. This heterogeneity remains relatively constant until the onset
 315 of the shear band formation and increases drastically afterwards. Qualitatively, the response along the
 316 shear band is similar. Quantitatively, variations exist similarly to the measured heterogeneity of the initial
 317 state.

318 The contact fabric of specimen HNEA01 is substantially more anisotropic in the initial state, in
 319 comparison to all other specimens, see also Table 1. Similarly to the stress ratio, fabric anisotropy reaches
 320 its peak earlier than the other Hostun sand specimens and decreases afterwards to an approximately steady
 321 value of 0.45. The high initial anisotropy arises from a strong preferential orientation of contact normals
 322 in the vertical direction, as visualised and discussed in [89]. This in turn means that the contacts are
 323 already aligned with the major principal stress direction and can thus sustain the applied loading. As the
 324 fabric in the other specimens is initially more isotropic, the contacts require more deformation to align
 325 with the loading direction. This can be the cause for the peak stress ratio being reached at a lower axial
 326 strain in test HNEA01.

Figure 5: Evolution of fabric anisotropy in the observation windows vs. global axial strain inside (dashed line) and outside (continuous line) the emerging shear band for (a) Hostun sand; (b) Caicos ooids. Note that fabric anisotropy is normalized by the specific volume of the measured volume as defined in Eqs. (1) and (2).

327 The evolution of fabric anisotropy is very similar in the two Caicos ooids specimens. Inside the shear
 328 band, it increases until reaching a pronounced peak, and then decreases to a steady value. It is remarkable
 329 that fabric anisotropy inside the shear band follows the macroscopic stress ratio very closely, as already
 330 noted by [86]. Similarly to the void ratio, the onset of strain localisation occurs at approximately 1 %
 331 axial strain, considerably earlier than in the Hostun sand specimens. This is due to the round shape

of the grains, which facilitates the emergence of a narrow shear band [88] when compared to the more angular Hostun sand grains. This is also the reason why Hostun sand samples reach a steady state later: angular grains cause interlocking, which hinders strain localisation and results in a wider shear band.

At large strains, fabric anisotropy inside the shear band tends to similar values for each of the two materials. However, the only Hostun sand specimen that possibly reaches a critical state (in that both stress ratio and void ratio level off, see Fig. 2(a – b)) is HNEA01. For the other two Hostun specimens, the void ratio does not reach a steady state at large axial strains (see Fig. 2(b)). Fabric anisotropy inside the shear band of HNEA01 reaches a steady value of approximately 0.45, whereas the fabric anisotropies of the other specimens are still decreasing at the end of the test. It can be observed, however, that they seem to approach a similar value as HNEA01.

Both Caicos ooids specimens reach a critical state and show a similar fabric anisotropy of approximately 0.45 inside the shear band. Although the specimens initially have a different fabric anisotropy, they gradually evolve to the same fabric anisotropy inside the shear band at critical state, which is in agreement with the existence of a unique value of the critical state anisotropy within ACST.

Finally, it should be noted that the curves of fabric anisotropy *vs.* axial strain are much smoother for Caicos ooids than for Hostun sand. This is due to the higher accuracy with which contact orientations (and thus contact fabric) are measured for round grains as compared to angular grains [82].

3.4. Coordination number

A simple, yet important quantity describing contacts is the coordination number, *i.e.*, the number of contacts per particle. Although it is not used in the fabric evolution law proposed in [49], we briefly present its evolution for completeness. The average coordination number Z in a set of contacting particles is defined as

$$Z = 2 \frac{N_c}{N_p}, \quad (4)$$

with N_p and N_c being the total number of particles and contacts, respectively. The basis for the measurement of Z is the detection of contacts, the accuracy of which depends on the shape of the particles (see [82, 99]). However, the actual values of Z are not necessarily relevant, and it is rather the qualitative evolution of the coordination number that matters.

The evolution of the coordination number inside and outside the shear band is shown in Fig. 6 for both Hostun sand and Caicos ooids. Hostun sand specimens HNMWTC02 and HNMWTC05 have a very similar initial Z , whereas HNEA01 has a lower initial coordination number (which is consistent with a higher initial void ratio, see Fig. 2(b)). After the onset of strain localisation, the coordination number strongly decreases inside the shear band, whereas it stays relatively constant outside. Similar to fabric

Figure 6: Evolution of coordination number in the observation windows with global axial strain inside (dashed line) and outside (continuous line) the emerging shear band for (a) Hostun sand; (b) Caicos ooids.

359 anisotropy, the coordination number inside the shear band reaches a steady value at approximately 8 %
 360 global axial strain for HNEA01. For the other two Hostun sand specimens, the evolution of Z shows a
 361 tendency to slow down and tends towards a steady value at the end of the tests, although for these two
 362 tests the void ratio does not (Fig. 2(b)). In an earlier analysis [86] of contact fabric evolution in two
 363 of the five tests analysed here, it was found that the evolution of Z is more sensitive to changes in the
 364 local microstructure than that of void ratio. Therefore, it is reasonable to argue that HNMWTC02 and
 365 HNMWTC05 are in fact close to reaching a steady state inside the shear band.

366 For the Caicos ooids specimens, the coordination number evolves in a similar way in the two tests.
 367 After the onset of strain localisation, the coordination number inside the shear band decreases and rapidly
 368 reaches a steady value, whereas it stays constant or slightly increases outside. The initial value of Z in
 369 specimen COEA04 is lower outside the shear band than inside, which also corresponds to a higher initial
 370 void ratio (see Fig. 3(b)). As already observed for contact fabric anisotropy, the coordination number
 371 reaches a steady and unique value at the end of the tests on Caicos ooids.

372 3.5. Implications of experimental results for CST and ACST

373 In this section, the experimental results presented above are analysed in the light of CST and ACST.
 374 According to CST, both stress ratio q/p and void ratio e should be unique (*i.e.*, independent of initial
 375 conditions) at critical state. ACST brings the additional condition that also fabric anisotropy F should
 376 be unique at critical state.

377 An important issue is whether the achieved strains inside the shear bands are sufficiently large for

critical state conditions to be actually attained in the experiments. For Hostun sand, the only test in which the stress ratio q/p becomes steady at the end of the test is HNEA01. At the end of the other two tests, the stress ratio is still slowly evolving (and higher than the final value in HNEA01). The samples HNMWTC02 and HNMWTC05 are still dilating at the end of the test, while the void ratio has reached a steady state at the end of test HNEA01. In summary, the tests on Hostun sand are inconclusive with respect to the validity of CST. As for Caicos ooids, tests COEA01 and COEA04 show a clear steady state for both stress ratio q/p and void ratio e at the end of the test. The final value of the stress ratio is the same in the two tests. This is also the case for the final void ratio — although some slight differences are observed. Hence, these tests essentially conform to CST.

As far as the requirements of ACST are concerned, in the case of Hostun sand, a steady state for fabric anisotropy F is attained only in test HNEA01, while F is still evolving at the end of tests HNMWTC02 and HNMWTC05. It is possible that if larger strains were achieved, then the asymptotic fabric anisotropy in all these tests would be the same (as expected by ACST). It is interesting that similar trends are observed for the coordination number Z , which is another descriptor of microstructure. Note that the coordination number in test HNMWTC02 is smaller than in test HNMWTC05, due to the larger confining pressure. For Caicos ooids, fabric anisotropy in both tests reaches a clear steady state, with equal F in both tests. The same qualitative result is obtained for the coordination number Z . Overall, the results for Caicos ooids clearly conform to ACST; those for Hostun sand appear to be compatible, but the achieved strains were insufficiently large to draw a strong conclusion.

4. Modelling the evolution of fabric anisotropy inside shear bands

In this section, the fabric evolution law developed in [49] is employed to simulate the evolution of fabric anisotropy, for the two materials studied, and the predicted evolution is compared to the experimental results. In the interpretation of the experimental results, it is assumed that the plastic strain is equal to the total strain, which may not be appropriate outside the shear band where the plastic strains are smaller. Therefore, the evolution of fabric is only simulated inside the shear bands.

The fabric evolution law proposed in [49] is summarised in Section 4.1. The determination of the model parameters is given in Section 4.2. The comparison of the evolution of fabric anisotropy between the experimental results and the model predictions is presented in Section 4.3.

4.1. Fabric evolution law

The adopted fabric evolution law is that developed in [49], given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{F}, \theta_s, \eta, \psi, \dot{\epsilon}_q^p) = h \left\{ F_c(\theta_s) - \mathbf{F} : \mathbf{n} \cdot \exp(m(M - \eta) + \psi) \right\} \dot{\epsilon}_q^p \quad (5)$$

408 where F_c is the critical-state fabric anisotropy (dependent on the Lode angle θ_s of the stress tensor), $\dot{\epsilon}_q^p$ is
 409 the deviatoric part of the plastic strain rate, the loading direction \mathbf{n} is defined as $\mathbf{n} \equiv \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_q^p}{\|\dot{\epsilon}_q^p\|}$, η and M are
 410 the stress ratios defined in Eq. (3), and h and m are two model parameters. As described in [49], the term
 411 $\mathbf{F} : \mathbf{n}$ represents the combined effect of the microstructure and loading direction. The state parameter ψ
 412 is defined by $\psi = e - e_c(p)$ in [87]. For given mean effective stress p , the critical state void ratio $e_c = e_c(p)$
 413 is estimated by

$$e_c(p) = e_\Gamma - \xi \left(\frac{p}{p_a} \right)^\alpha \quad (6)$$

414 where e_Γ , ξ and α are dependent on the material; p_a is the (reference) atmospheric pressure. The model
 415 parameters in the fabric evolution law involve well-established parameters (those in the critical state line
 416 and the critical state stress ratio M) as well as a small number of additional parameters (F_c , h and m).

417 Based on observations of results from DEM simulations in [40, 67] and experimental studies in [86]
 418 where the Lode angle of stress is constant, it is noted that at critical state, fabric and loading direction are
 419 coaxial. In [100] the loading direction was based on the stress tensor, and it was found that the contact
 420 normal fabric tensor always tends to be coaxial with the stress tensor under cyclic loading, regardless of
 421 the specimen density and cyclic failure mode. Therefore, at the critical state the condition $\mathbf{n}_F : \mathbf{n} = 1$
 422 holds for various loading conditions. In addition, at critical state the stress ratio η attains its critical value
 423 M and the state parameter ψ becomes zero. Hence, the fabric anisotropy F reaches the critical state F_c ,
 424 irrespective of the development of the deviatoric plastic strain $\dot{\epsilon}_q^p$. Thus, in the critical state $F_c = \mathbf{F}_c : \mathbf{n}$,
 425 which closely resembles the normalisation $A_c = 1$ by Li and Dafalias [61]. Therefore, the fabric evolution
 426 law Eq. (5) is consistent with ACST according to which $F = F_c$ at the critical state.

427 4.2. Calibration of model parameters

428 In the current simulations, three parameters (e_Γ , ξ and α) for the critical state line given by Eq.(6)
 429 and four parameters (F_c , M , h and m) for the fabric evolution law Eq.(5) are required.

430 As discussed in [49], since it is not feasible to separate elastic and plastic strain from the experimental
 431 results and elastic strain in granular soils are generally small, the deviatoric plastic strain rate tensor $\dot{\epsilon}_q^p$
 432 is approximated by the deviatoric strain rate tensor $\dot{\epsilon}_q$. The strain increments $\dot{\epsilon}_q$ are calculated from
 433 the displacement increments of sand particles inside shear bands, using the expression for the strain
 434 tensor of Bagi [97]. The accuracy of this method has been established in [101]. Note that such strain

435 increments $\dot{\epsilon}_q$ are slightly different from the strain increments in the shear band determined from particle
 436 total displacements, since for each strain increment the reference configuration for particle displacement
 437 increments is the previous x-ray scan, but not the first x-ray image of the sand sample.

438 The stress ratio $\eta = q/p$ required in the evolution law Eq. (5) is taken equal to that measured for the
 439 whole sample. The reason is that the interparticle contact forces are not measured in the experiments,
 440 and hence it is not possible to determine the average stress inside the shear band. This is an assumption
 441 to be verified in future studies, using DEM simulations.

442 To calculate the state parameter $\psi = e - e_c(p)$, the void ratio e measured inside shear bands is adopted,
 443 whereas the critical state void ratio $e_c(p)$ is determined from Eq. (6). Since the experiments for Hostun
 444 sand involve only two different confining pressures (100 kPa and 400 kPa) and those for Caicos ooids
 445 involve only one confining pressure (100 kPa), it is not possible to calibrate the three parameters e_Γ ,
 446 ξ and α . Therefore, the value of the exponent $\alpha = 0.9$ that was proposed in [98] for the macroscopic
 447 critical state line of Hostun sand is adopted. For Hostun sand, the other two parameters (e_Γ and ξ) for
 448 the critical state line are determined from the void ratio inside the shear band at the end of the test. For
 449 Caicos ooids, ξ is assumed to be the same as for Hostun sand, whereas e_Γ is directly determined from the
 450 critical state void ratio in the shear band. The calibrated parameters for the critical state line are given
 451 in Table 2.

Table 2: Model parameters used for the critical state line (Eq. (6)) and the fabric evolution law (Eq. (5))

	Critical state line			Fabric evolution law			
Material	e_Γ	ξ	α	M	F_c	h	m
Hostun Sand	0.961	0.015	0.9	1.6	0.34	30	0.1
Caicos ooids	0.822	0.015	0.9	1.5	0.33	65	0.85

452 For the fabric evolution law, the initial fabric (directly taken from that measured inside shear bands)
 453 is used as the initial condition. Since the strain increment (determined by Bagi’s method [97]) between
 454 two x-ray scans is large, it is divided into 100 uniformly spaced strain increments for the numerical
 455 integration of the fabric evolution law (note that when the number of strain increments is greater than
 456 10, the simulation results are the same). At intermediate strains (between two x-ray scans), the stress
 457 ratio η and the state parameter ψ are interpolated.

458 By substituting the interpolated deviatoric strain rate tensor $\dot{\epsilon}_q$, initial fabric \mathbf{F} , stress ratio η , and
 459 state parameter ψ into the fabric evolution law (Eq. (5)), the rate of fabric anisotropy is obtained. For
 460 Hostun sand, the parameters are determined from tests HNMWTC02 and HNMWTC05, while HNEA01
 461 is used as a ”blind test”. The parameters F_c , h and m used in the fabric evolution law have been obtained

462 by comparing the fabric anisotropy predicted by Eq. (5) with that measured inside shear bands, using a
 463 trial-and-error least-squares approach. The optimized parameters are given in Table 2.

464 4.3. Model simulations

465 Fig. 7 shows the predicted and measured evolution of fabric anisotropy F as a function of the deviatoric
 466 strain inside the shear band for the five tests.

Figure 7: Comparison of predicted and measured evolution of fabric anisotropy within shear bands: (a) Hostun sand; (b) Caicos ooids.

467 Qualitatively, the model simulations are in good agreement with the experimental results. Fabric
 468 anisotropy shows a distinct peak (especially for Caicos ooids), which has been well reproduced by the
 469 fabric evolution law. Quantitatively, for test HNMWTC02 the deviation between model simulations and
 470 experiments has a maximum value of 7.1% (when the local deviatoric strain $\epsilon_q = 33.3\%$) and an average
 471 value smaller than 5%. For test HNMWTC05, the maximum deviation is 11.9% (when $\epsilon_q = 13.6\%$),
 472 and the average deviation is 6%. For Caicos ooids, the simulations have a maximum deviation of 13.6%
 473 (when $\epsilon_q = 26.2\%$) for test COEA01 and 9.8% (when $\epsilon_q = 29.2\%$) for test COEA04, and an average
 474 deviation smaller than 5% for both tests. Overall, for the four tests used for the calibration of the model
 475 parameters, the model predictions agree well with the experiments when the deviatoric strain is smaller
 476 than 5%, with deviations smaller than 5%.

477 For the simulations of HNEA01 (a "blind test", *i.e.*, these test data have not been used in the
 478 calibration of the model parameters), the deviations between model simulations and experiments are
 479 larger than for the other cases (see black curves in Fig. 7(a)). The average deviation is about 20%, with
 480 a maximum value of 35.4% (when $\epsilon_q = 28.9\%$). At larger deformations, the fabric evolution law gives

481 larger fabric anisotropy than the one measured in the experiment. A possible reason is that the critical
482 state fabric (F_c) and stress ratio (M) in test HNEA01 are very different from those in the two tests that
483 have been used to calibrate the model parameters.

484 A detailed assessment of the accuracy of the fabric evolution law for fabric anisotropy is hampered by
485 the limited amount of experimental data (with their intrinsic uncertainties): (i) the number of x-ray scans
486 is limited, which makes it difficult to evaluate quantities like void ratio, stress ratio and strain increments
487 at intermediate strain levels, (ii) plastic strains could not be extracted from the experimental data, and
488 therefore these have been taken equal to the total strains, (iii) the number of confining pressure levels
489 considered did not allow for accurate calibration of the critical state line that is required in the fabric
490 evolution law, (iv) the number of grains present in the two observation windows is fairly small, and (v)
491 no data is available on local stresses inside the shear band, and therefore overall, average stresses have
492 been employed.

493 Overall, the fabric evolution law is capable of reproducing the evolution of fabric anisotropy of *real*
494 granular soils (rather than the idealised particles used in DEM simulations), and it is to be further
495 evaluated quantitatively by additional experiments with more x-ray scans in future studies.

496 5. Conclusions

497 Fabric anisotropy is very important to the behaviour of granular soils. The development of evolution
498 laws for fabric has greatly advanced since the formulation of ACST [61]. In general, experimental data
499 on fabric anisotropy for real granular soils are very limited, especially in the critical state.

500 Using x-ray tomography measurements, experimental data on fabric anisotropy inside shear bands
501 have been provided for two real granular soils. These data have been used to assess the validity of ACST
502 and the accuracy of a fabric evolution law which was previously developed using data from idealised DEM
503 simulations.

504 The main findings of this study are:

- 505 • Fabric anisotropy inside shear bands is larger than that outside shear bands; this is due to the smaller
506 deformation outside of the shear band, resulting in the development of limited fabric anisotropy.
- 507 • The experimental results for both materials are largely consistent with the classical CST.
- 508 • For Caicos ooids, fabric anisotropy and the coordination number clearly approach unique values at
509 large strain, irrespective of the initial fabric and void ratio.
- 510 • For Hostun sand, the results are less clear, but it seems that fabric anisotropy may be developing
511 toward unique asymptotic values at large strains, although initial fabric anisotropy, void ratio and
512 confining pressure are different.

- 513 • Overall, these experimental observations support ACST. The angularity of soil particles has signifi-
514 cant impact on the evolution of fabric anisotropy and coordination number: in the tests on rounded
515 Caicos ooids the critical state is approached more rapidly than in the tests on angular Hostun sand.
- 516 • The measured evolution of fabric anisotropy inside shear bands is fairly well predicted by the evo-
517 lution law proposed in [49], at least from a qualitative standpoint.

518 The obvious (and necessary) extension of this study should include more detailed information on fabric
519 evolution and the critical state, which can be obtained by performing many more x-ray scans during a
520 test, and shearing the specimens to larger strains. Also, a wider range of confinement pressures should
521 be investigated.

522 For future studies, other important issues related to the evolution of fabric anisotropy of granular soils
523 could also be investigated. In this study, the fabric tensor is based on contact normal orientations; it
524 would be of interest to also examine the evolution of other fabric tensors. In the experiments, the effects
525 of particle shape and possible particle breakage on fabric evolution could also be measured. The influence
526 of loading directions could also be investigated, by performing cyclic loading with larger amplitudes or
527 rotational shearing. Finally, in the evolution law for fabric anisotropy [49], it is assumed that the rate of
528 fabric change is proportional to the plastic strain rate. This is a strong assumption that can (and should)
529 be verified by analysing the experimental results from x-ray tomography.

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